

STRATEGIES FOR OPTIMAL SELECTION OF BUILDING MATERIALS IN INTERNATIONAL PRACTICE: ECONOMIC, ENVIRONMENTAL, AND TECHNOLOGICAL ASPECTS

Yarov Yu.

Kyrgyz National University named after Zhusup Balasagyn

Abstract

This article examines the main strategies for the optimal selection of construction materials (CM) in international practice, considering economic, ecological, and technological aspects. Key factors influencing material selection are analyzed, such as cost, availability, durability, energy efficiency, and environmental safety. The article also studies the impact of price instability in CM, caused by economic and external factors, on supplier selection and construction project planning. Special attention is given to the analysis of current practices in the use of CM in construction processes, taking into account their energy efficiency and sustainability.

Keywords: construction materials (CM), material selection, economic aspects, sustainable construction, energy efficiency, life cycle assessment, innovative materials.

Introduction

The selection of construction materials (CM) is an important stage at all phases of construction, from design to building operation. This process encompasses a wide range of factors, including economic feasibility, environmental safety, and technological efficiency. In recent decades, issues related to sustainable construction and minimizing environmental impact (EI) have gained particular importance. In this regard, the global CM market is constantly evolving and adapting. New innovative solutions are introduced every year. They are aimed at enhancing both the economic and environmental efficiency of construction.

Economic factors in CM selection include costs and long-term financial implications. These factors may also cover operational expenses, material lifespan, and their capacity to reduce building energy costs. At the same time, technological innovations play a critical role, providing new materials and technologies that improve building quality and durability while accelerating construction processes. Consequently, a thorough approach to material selection becomes essential to consider all aspects of their use and maximize benefits.

Environmental aspects of CM selection are of special significance within the global efforts to reduce carbon footprints and promote sustainable development.

The growing awareness of construction's EI and the tightening of environmental standards across countries are prompting construction companies to make more responsible choices when selecting CM. It is important to consider the environmental footprint of CM throughout its lifecycle and its potential for recycling and reuse. The aim of this study is to analyze strategies for optimal CM selection in international practice, taking into account economic, environmental, and technological factors.

Main part. Analysis of various aspects of CM selection

The economic aspects of CM selection are an essential topic in the context of residential and commercial building construction. Price volatility of materials can impact CM selection strategies, as companies and builders need to adapt to fluctuations in material costs. This may lead them to opt for more affordable or durable materials that help mitigate risks associated with price changes. The Production Price Index (PPI) for construction components and materials is an index reflecting changes in prices for CM that producers receive for their products. According to statistics [1], since 2019, the PPI for construction components and CM has shown significant fluctuations (fig. 1).

Figure 1. PPI of construction components and materials in the U.S. from 2003 to 2023

These changes may be linked to global economic events such as the COVID-19 pandemic, supply chain issues, inflation, and other economic factors. Therefore, the recent price instability of CM has forced companies to seek new material selection strategies that can help minimize financial risks. Such practices may include the use of local materials, long-term contracts, or selecting components with more stable prices. Amid price instability, it is particularly important to consider the cost of CM at the time of purchase and in the long term, including operational and maintenance expenses.

Technological aspects of CM selection include innovations in material production and recycling. They also encompass a wide range of issues related to their application in construction. The development of the construction industry is directly tied to advancements in production technologies, as well as the optimization of various processes: from raw material extraction to building assembly and operation. Each new technology brings opportunities to enhance the quality, sustainability, and functionality of construction projects. This, in turn, affects material selection, their long-term performance, and energy efficiency.

A key factor in the technological selection of CM is their production characteristics and ability to meet specified performance requirements. Modern CM should possess high strength, durability, resistance to external influences (e.g., exposure to harsh environments, temperature fluctuations, moisture, and ultraviolet radiation). This also contributes to thermal and sound insulation properties. In recent years, particular attention has been paid to materials with improved characteristics that allow for more efficient resource use, such as energy-efficient and high-tech building components.

One of the most important tools for assessing the environmental friendliness and sustainability of CM is the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) method [2]. This approach helps determine the total environmental footprint of a material at all stages of its lifecycle: from raw material extraction, production, and transportation to usage and disposal or recycling. The LCA method helps take into account the direct EI (e.g., CO₂ emissions during production) and various factors such as water consumption, energy use, waste generation, and recycling. Implementing LCA in construction allows for the selection of materials that best align with sustainability principles and minimize negative EI.

Different countries worldwide have various environmental standards and regulations aimed at reducing the EI of construction [3]. In the U.S., the LEED (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design) system is widely used, promoting the use of environmentally safe CM and technologies, such as recycled materials, energy-saving systems, and CM with low carbon footprints. Integrating Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) factors into construction practices also allows companies to align with sustainable and responsible standards [4]. A well-implemented Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) strategy further enhances this commitment. It focuses on areas like reducing carbon emissions, responsibly sourcing materials, and fostering positive community relationships. These

approaches strengthen the company's reputation and meet the growing expectations of stakeholders.

Selection of efficient CM in global practice

One of the most notable trends in construction technology is the use of innovative CM, such as nanomaterials, composites, biomaterials, and shape-memory materials. These materials enhance the physical and mechanical properties of construction projects and significantly reduce their environmental footprint.

Polymer composite materials are becoming one of the most popular options in construction. They combine light weight, strength, and durability, along with high resistance to moisture, aggressive chemicals, and temperature fluctuations. Polymer composites consist of reinforcing fibers (such as fiberglass, carbon fiber, or Kevlar) and a polymer matrix (e.g., epoxy or polyester resins). They are used to create structural elements for buildings, such as panels, slabs, partitions, and for manufacturing reinforced concrete structures. Advantages include lightweight, high tensile and compressive strength, durability, and moisture resistance. Fiberglass and carbon fiber composites are used in the production of facade elements, window frames, and engineering communications. These materials have excellent corrosion resistance and chemical resistance. It makes them ideal for use in aggressive external environments.

Biomaterials, or materials based on natural components, are becoming an important element in sustainable construction. These materials are highly eco-friendly, can be recycled and reduce negative EI. Although wood has been used in construction for centuries, new treatment technologies and improvements in its properties have enabled the creation of wood composites with enhanced characteristics. Examples include glued laminated timber, fiberboard, particleboard, and wood panels with increased strength and resistance to environmental influences. Natural CM, such as clay and limestone, are used in various forms, from bricks and tiles to plaster and finishing materials. The enhancement of the properties of these materials with additives make them more resistant to external influences, durable, and fire-resistant. Various modern biomaterials can offer advantages such as reducing water absorption by 40%, lowering energy consumption by 8,7%, enhancing acoustic absorption by 6,7% [5].

Shape Memory Alloys (SMA) are metal alloys that can change shape in response to temperature changes or other factors. They can be used to create self-regulating structural elements, such as facades that alter their shape based on temperature or sunlight. Titanium and nickel alloys are used to create flexible and durable structural elements that can return to their original shape after deformation, reducing the need for maintenance and repairs.

Phase Change Materials (PCM) are materials capable of changing their phase (e.g., from solid to liquid or vice versa) under specific temperature conditions. These materials are actively used in construction to improve thermal insulation and increase building energy efficiency. In the context of CM selection, they represent a promising tool for creating comfortable and energy-efficient spaces, reducing the need for heating

and cooling. Modern PCM are available on the market and are used in various building components (table 1).

Table 1.

Manufacturers of PCM used for building applications [6]

Manufacturer	Product	Latent heat capacity (kJ/kg)	PCM material	Type	Building product
Dupont	Energain	515	Paraffin wax compound	Organic	Thermal mass panels
Armstrong World Industries	Coolzone	119	BASF micronal	Organic	Chilled roof system
Knauf	Comfort board, Smartboard 23&26	200	BASF micronal	Organic	Gypsum board with micro-capsules of PCM
Salca	K-Block	590	Salt hydrate	Inorganic	Mat filled with PCM

Nanomaterials are becoming increasingly sought after in the construction industry due to their unique properties, which significantly enhance strength, durability, and resistance to external influences. Adding nanoparticles (such as titanium oxide or graphene) to concrete improves its strength, reduces porosity, and increases resistance to moisture and chemical exposure. Studies in 2024 show, that they are related to increased durability, increased mechanical strength (>20 %), reduced thermal conductivity, and self-cleaning capability [7]. Nanoconcretes can be used under extreme temperature conditions or high mechanical loads and offer superior thermal insulation properties.

Nanotechnology is also used to create ultra-thin coatings with water-repellent, dirt-resistant, or anti-corrosive properties. This can significantly extend the lifespan of buildings, particularly in harsh climate conditions. Graphene is another promising material for strengthening concrete and construction composites, possesses exceptional mechanical properties. Graphene-based CM is several times stronger than steel while weighing half as much. This material opens new possibilities for creating ultra-strong and lightweight construction structures [8].

Technological aspects of CM selection provide vast opportunities for innovation in construction. Nanomaterials, polymer composites, biomaterials, and new construction technologies enhance the strength and durability of structures and reduce the EI of construction. Implementing such technologies could significantly transform the CM market, making it more sustainable, energy-efficient, and eco-friendly.

Conclusion

The selection of CM plays a vital role in achieving both economic efficiency and sustainability in modern building projects. With advancements in technology, materials like nanomaterials, biomaterials, and composites offer enhanced strength, durability, and reduced EI, supporting long-term sustainability goals. The integration of environmentally friendly and energy-efficient materials addresses the challenges posed by climate change, as it emphasizes the importance of innovative solutions that optimize resource use and resilience. As the construction industry continues to

evolve, the careful choice of materials will remain essential for creating structures that are both efficient and ecologically responsible.

References

1. Materials and components for construction producer price index in the U.S. from 1947 to 2023 / Statista // URL: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/195382/us-producer-price-index-of-construction-materials-since-1990/> (date of application: 01.11.2024).
2. Barbhuiya S., Das B.B. Life Cycle Assessment of construction materials: Methodologies, applications and future directions for sustainable decision-making // Case Studies in Construction Materials. 2023. P. e02326.
3. Konstantinov D.S., Solovyev K.A., Gazizyanov A.I., Sazonov A.I. Implementation of environmental practices in business strategies: analysis of sustainable management models // First Economic Journal. 2024. No. 7(349). P. 133-141.
4. Abdullina L., Bobovnikova A., Zrazhevskiy A. ESG-factors and CSR-strategy impact on the investment attractiveness of USA companies // Proceedings of the XLIII International Multidisciplinary Conference «Recent Scientific Investigation». Primedia E-launch LLC. Shawnee, USA. 2023.
5. Chen L., Zhang Y., Chen Z., Dong Y., Jiang Y., Hua J., Liu Y., Osman A.I., Farghali M., Huang L., Rooney D.W. Biomaterials technology and policies in the building sector: a review // Environmental Chemistry Letters. 2024. Vol. 22. No. 2. P. 715-50.
6. Zhang S., Ocloń P., Klemeš J.J., Michoreczyk P., Pielichowska K., Pielichowski K. Renewable energy systems for building heating, cooling and electricity production with thermal energy storage // Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews. 2022. Vol. 165. P. 112560.
7. Macías-Silva M.A., Cedeño-Muñoz J.S., Morales-Paredes C.A., Tinizaray-Castillo R., Perero-Espinoza G.A., Rodríguez-Díaz J.M., Jarre-Castro C.M. Nanomaterials in construction industry: An overview of their properties and contributions in building house

// Case Studies in Chemical and Environmental Engineering. 2024. P. 100863.

8. Asim N., Badiei M., Samsudin N.A., Mohamad M., Razali H., Soltani S., Amin N. Application of

graphene-based materials in developing sustainable infrastructure: An overview // Composites Part B: Engineering. 2022. Vol. 245. P. 110188.